

SilaCrown Ethers: Synthesis and Influence on Ion Flux Across Myocardial Cell Membranes

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Abstract

There are over 100 known channelopathy diseases which are generally described as diseases associated with transport of ions across cell membranes. They include cardiovascular, degenerative neuropathy and renal diseases. For the most part channelopathy diseases have been considered “undruggable.” Crown ethers have been shown to have physiological effects ascribed to their ionophoric properties. However, high levels of toxicity precluded interest in evaluation as therapeutics. We prepared silacrown analogs of crown ethers. Initial studies focused on examples of large ring silacrown ethers having at least fourteen ring atoms with at least one lipophilic or hydrophobic substituent on the ring and/or on the silicon atom. The synthesis of silacrown ethers, ionophoric behavior, preliminary toxicity studies, evaluation in human and rabbit atrial tissue and preliminary studies in cardiac myocyte cell lines will be presented and compared to their carbon analogs. For HL-1 cells, an atrial muscle cell line, three different responses were observed for the compounds tested: no effect on Ca^{+2} or response to KCl-depolarization, strong inhibition of Ca^{+2} transients with some residual response to KCl-depolarization, and inhibition of Ca^{+2} transients and no subsequent response to KCl-depolarization.

Outline

- Introduction to crown ethers and silacrowns
- Overview of Ion Channels and Channelopathy Diseases
- Vascular Tissue Response to Ions
- Acute Toxicity Studies of Silacrowns versus Crown Ethers
- Studies of Cardiomyocyte Response to Silacrowns
- Conclusions

Crown-6 Ethers: Ionophores

Silacrowns ethers were initially developed as low toxicity, economical alternatives to crown ethers for phase transfer catalysis.

B. Arkles *et al*, *Organometallics*, 2(3), 454-457, 1983 DOI: 10.1021/om00075a018

Elaborating Silacrown Structures

Ring Size
 Ring Substitution
 Functionality
 Hydrolytic Stability

Silacrown Synthesis

Silacrown Synthesis in 2 stage distillation of volatile components from equilibrating mixtures

Silacrowns: Historical Applications as Ionophores

Enabled cyanoacrylate adhesion to inhibitory surfaces: cellulose (wood), tissues (skin)

Na⁺ and K⁺ ions inhibit polymerization of cyanoacrylates

J. Liu, (Loctite) US Pat. 4,906,317, 1990
A. Hirawai, (Toagosei) Jap. Pat. 609,027, 1985

Tissue Adhesives, Mesh Fixation,
Advanced Medical Solutions

Ion Channels

Ion channels are composed of membrane proteins, glycoproteins, phospholipids, that create gated pathways for the movement of ions through cell membranes.

Ion transport Across Membranes

- Passive Flux
- Voltage Gated
- Active Gated
- Mechanically (stimuli) gated

KcsA potassium channel

Calcium Release Activated Channel (CRAC) protein

H. Dong, M. Klein et al, PNAS, 2013, 110, 173

D. Bucher, M. Klein et al, Biophysical Chemistry, 2006, 124, 292

V. Carnevale, M. Klein, J. Phys. Chem. B, 2013, 117, 3782

Ion Channels - Why should we care?

Dysfunction of Ion Channels Can Lead to.....

"I think that ion channels are the most important single class of proteins that exist in the human body, or any body for that matter."

"Ion channels are involved in every thought, every perception, every movement, every heartbeat."

– *Clay Armstrong*

Recipient of Albert Lasker Award for Basic Medical Research

- Seizures
- Heart Attacks
- Movement disorders
- Pain, itch
- Vision, hearing, smell and taste disorders
- Memory disorders
- Developmental disorders
- Immune disorders
- Kidney disorders
- Diabetes
- Cancer

Examples of Channelopathy Related Disease

- Microglial ion channels/transporters for neurodegenerative disease, **ischemic stroke, traumatic brain injury and neuropathic pain**
 - Electrolyte transport-related mechanisms for the development of severe inherited renal disorders, autosomal dominant (AD) and recessive (AR) forms of **polycystic kidney disease (PKD)**
 - Impaired sodium transport is an upstream pathogenic factor in **inflammatory bowel disease (IBD)**
Ca²⁺/cAMP signaling pathways and the role of these pathways in **Parkinson's disease and epilepsy**
 - Loss-of-function mutations in chloride transporters cause a wide variety of human diseases, including **cystic fibrosis, secretory diarrhea, kidney stones, salt-wasting nephropathy, myotonia, osteopetrosis, hearing loss, and goiter**
- * Ion channels at the membrane of a cardiomyocyte appear to be major sources of channel dysfunction during **cardiac arrhythmias, hypertension and heart failure**

Ion concentration differential across the cell membrane

Intra- and extracellular ion concentrations (mmol/L)

Element	Ion	Extracellular	Intracellular	Ratio
Sodium	Na ⁺	135 - 145	10	14:1
Potassium	K ⁺	3.5 - 5.0	155	1:30
Chloride	Cl ⁻	95 - 110	10 - 20	4:1
Calcium	Ca ²⁺	2	10 ⁻⁴	2 x 10 ⁴ :1

Although intracellular Ca²⁺ content is about 2 mM, most of this is bound or sequestered in intracellular organelles (mitochondria and sarcoplasmic reticulum).

Ion	Radius, Å
Sodium Na ⁺	0.95
Calcium Ca ²⁺	1.06
Potassium K ⁺	1.38

Crown Ether	Cavity Radius, Å
12-crown-4	0.6-0.75
15-crown-5	0.86-0.92
18-crown-6	1.34-1.55
21-crown-7	1.7-2.1

Vascular tissue contractile response as a function of crown ether concentration

R. Ginsburg et al, unpublished

Hierarchy

Membrane

Cell

Tissue

Organ

Crown Ether Acute Oral Toxicity

Crown ether	Oral-mouse, LD50*	Dimethyl Silacrown	Oral-rat, LD50**
12-C-4	2830 mg/kg		
15-C-5	2100 mg/kg	14-C-5	9,900 mg/kg
18-C-6	1590 mg/kg	17-C-6	>5000 mg/kg

Cyclohexyl Crown ether	Oral-mouse, LD50*	Cyclohexyl Silacrown	Oral-rat, LD50**
Di-Cy-18-C-6	176 mg/kg	Cy-14-C-5	>5000 mg/kg
D-Cy-24-C-8	75 mg/kg		

*S. Gad et al, "Thirteen Cationic Ionophores: Their Acute Toxicity, Neurobehavioral and Membrane Effects," Drug and Chemical Toxicology, 8(6), 451-468 (1985)

**B. Arkles et al, US Pat. 11,749,568, 2022

Comparative Transport and Hydrolytic Stability

TRANSPORT OF POTASSIUM PICRATE, (M/1 MIN) 10⁸

Carrier	Rate	Ratio Crown/Glycol
Sila-20-crown-7	400	5.7
Hexaethyleneglycol	70	
Sila-14-crown-5	19	9.5
Tetraethyleneglycol	2	

HYDROLYSIS OF SILA-14-CROWN-5 IN ISOTONIC SALINE SOLUTION, pH 7.4*

Time (m)	% silacrown	% tetraethylene glycol†
0	100	—
5	90	—
25	44	34
66	37	38

K. Pannell *et al*, Pharmacology Biochemistry and Behavior, 21 (Suppl. 1), 77-80, 1984;
[doi.org/10.1016/0091-3057\(84\)90167](https://doi.org/10.1016/0091-3057(84)90167)

Cardiomyocytes and Action Potential

- Action potential can be defined as the rapid changes in the membrane potential.
- The changes occur due to changes in the permeability of the membrane to ions.
- In the extracellular fluid there is a high concentration of Na^+ ions and a low concentration of K^+ ions.
- Intracellularly there is a relatively high concentration of K^+ ions and a low concentration of Na^+ ions.
- The sodium-potassium pump present in the membrane, regulates the respective concentration of these ions.

- Intracellular (cytosol) the resting potential (phase 4) is **negatively** charged compared to extracellularly **positive** charged.

Action Potential Phases

Action potential generated by a ventricular cardiomyocyte

- **There are 5 phases, numbered (0-4)**
- **Phase 4:** Is the resting membrane potential.
- **Phase 0:** is immediate/rapid depolarization
- Results from a Na^+ ion influx into the cell by the fast channels opening.
- The fast Na^+ channels opening is depending on the membrane potential at the time of excitation.
- **Phase 1:** slight repolarization, is due to closure of the fast Na^+ channels, causing an end to depolarization, after overshooting
- **Phase 2:** plateau of action potential
- **Phase 3:** The potassium channels are open which cause potassium ions to go into the extracellular compartment. The is net loss of positive charge causes the cell to repolarize.
- **Phase 4:** back to resting membrane potential will remain in this state until another action potential is generated.

Experiments with Cardiac Muscle Cells

HL-1 cells - a cardiac muscle cell line that contracts and retains phenotypic characteristics of the adult cardiomyocyte.

Atrial muscle cell line with plasma membrane and sarcoplasmic reticulum Ca^{2+} channels and ability to give spontaneous Ca^{2+} transients driven by action potentials.

Ca^{2+} transients initiate muscle contraction in skeletal and cardiac muscles;
[muscle relaxation](#) in [smooth muscles](#)

Phase 2 begins when the slow Ca^{++} influx concentration triggers a much greater release of Ca^{++} ions stored in the sarcoplasmic reticulum (SR). The SR Ca^{++} release induces cardiac myofibril contraction. Contraction begins about halfway through Phase 2. Phase 2 plateaus for about 200 milliseconds, after which contraction stops, and the Ca^{++} channels are closed.

Ca²⁺ transients are synchronized across multiple cells

Dye fluoresces **Green** with Ca²⁺

Spontaneous cytosolic Ca²⁺ transients are calcium-dependent. Removing extracellular calcium stops the rapid Ca²⁺ transients. When calcium is added back, they restart, but much broader with Ca²⁺ transients that are synchronized across multiple cells within the cell monolayer. Partial cell depolarization with addition of extracellular KCl restarts the rapid spontaneous Ca²⁺ transients.

Hajnoczky, G. & Thomas, A. Minimal requirements for calcium oscillations driven by the IP 3 receptor. *EMBO J* **16**, 3533–3543²¹ (1997).

Silacrowns for Scoping Studies

- Cyclohexylmethylsila-14-crown-5
- Dimethylsila-14-cyclohexylcrown-5
- Dimethylsila-17-cyclohexylcrown-6

Controls

Cyclohexano-15-crown-5

Structural control- considered to be Na⁺ ionophore

Dimethylsila-17-crown-6

K⁺ ionophore- but negative control in human aortic studies

Dicyclohexano-24-crown-8.

Positive control- demonstrated activity in human aortic tissue

Calcium Ion Flux - Responses Observed:

- No effect on Ca^{2+} transient or response to KCl-depolarization
- Inhibition of Ca^{2+} transients no subsequent response to KCl-depolarization
- **Strong inhibition of Ca^{2+} transients partial restorative response to KCl-depolarization**

B. Arkles et al, J. Inorganic Biochemistry, 2025, 265, 112814

Inhibition of Ca²⁺ transients, no subsequent response to KCl-depolarization

DB 30-C-10. Effective in slowing Ca²⁺ transients at 10-20 uM, peak of Ca²⁺ release at 50 uM. Blocks the response to KCl-induced depolarization.

No effect on Ca²⁺ transient

B-15-C-5. No consistent changes in frequency or amplitude.

Inhibition of Ca²⁺ transients, no subsequent response to KCl-depolarization

DCH-24-C-8. Ca²⁺ spike frequency and amplitude are decreased at 20 uM, and at 30 uM there is a single broad peak of Ca²⁺ and then the oscillations stop. Little or no effect after the addition of 50 uM KCl.

Strong inhibition of Ca²⁺ transients, partial restorative response to KCl-depolarization

DMSCH-17-C-6. Effective in inhibiting Ca²⁺ transients at 10-50 uM. Inhibits but does not completely block the response to KCl-induced depolarization.

Concentration necessary to inhibit completely the Ca²⁺ transient

Compound	Concentration
1 - DCH-24-C-8	30 μ M
2 - DMSCH-17-C-6	10 μM
3 - DCH-18-C-6	20 μ M
7- CHMS-14-C-5	50 μ M
8 - DB-21-C-7	20 μ M
9 - DB-24-C-8	10 μ M
12 – DB-30-C-10	20 μ M

Summary of compound activity

No effect on Ca²⁺ transient:

Inhibits Ca²⁺ transient, restorative KCl response after titration:

Inhibits Ca²⁺ transient, no KCl response after titration:

Pressure myograph system for recording arterial contraction/relaxation

Ex-vivo example depicted above for clarity- actual experiments performed *in vivo*.

Mesenteric arteriole dilation in anesthetized live mouse

DMSCH-17-C-6 causes a lower artery dilation at 30 μ M - consistent with the vasodilatory effects of acetylcholine

PE = phenylephrine - contraction agent

Potential Mechanisms of Action

- Active crowns acting as K^+ ionophores to hyperpolarize the plasma membrane, and hence suppress action potentials.
- Ring sizes <17 atoms do not complex Ca^{+2} or K^+ ; >17 ring atoms complex Ca^{+2} weakly, K^+ strongly- K^+ ions can displace Ca^{+2} ; very large ring sizes disrupt membrane (lipid bilayer) structure.

Conclusions

- Physiological activity of silacrowns observed with ring size of 17 atoms or greater.
- Dimethylsila-17-cyclohexylcrown-6 demonstrates strong inhibition of Ca^{2+} transients and partial restorative response to K^{+} depolarization in myocardial cell lines.
- Aortic tissue response correlates with single cell fluorescence in initial studies.
- Silacrowns are potential therapeutic agents in hypertension, arrhythmias and heart failure through a potassium/calcium channel mechanism of action and worthy of further study.

Currently there no antihypertensive agents in use or in pipeline with a primary potassium mechanism of action.

Ion flux Across Myocardial Cell Membranes as influenced by Crown and Silacrown Ethers

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References

1. B. Arkles *et al*, *Organometallics*, 2(3), 454-457, 1983 DOI: 10.1021/om00075a018
2. J. Liu, (Loctite) US Pat. 4,906,317, 1990
3. A. Hirawai, (Toagosei) Jap. Pat. 609,027, 1985
4. K. Pannell *et al*, *Pharmacology Biochemistry and Behavior*, 21 (Suppl. 1), 77-80, 1984; doi:10.1016/0091-3057(84)90167
5. K. Pannell *et al*, *J. Membrane Science*, 1987, 32, 83-91, doi.org: 10.1016/S0376-7388
6. S. Gad et al, *Drug and Chemical Toxicology*, 8(6), 451-468, 1985.
7. R. Ginsburg et al, *Circ. Res.* 416–421, 1984.
8. B. Arkles *et al*, US Pat. 11,749,568, 2022
9. M. Klein *et al*, *Biophysical Chemistry*, 2006, 124, 292
10. M. Klein *et al*, *PNAS*, 2013, 110, 1732 DOI:10.1073/pnas.1316969110
11. V. Carnevale et al, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 2013, 117, 3782
12. A. Thomas *et al*, Minimal requirements for calcium oscillations driven by the IP 3 receptor. *EMBO J* **16**, 3533–3543, 1997
13. B. Arkles *et al*, *J. Inorganic Biochemistry*, 2025, 265, 112814 DOI:10.1016/j.jinorgbio.2024.112814